

Magnetic, Spectral and Thermogravimetric Studies of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Bis(Benzoylacetato) Nickel(II) with Nitrogen Donors

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Several mixed ligand complexes of bis(benzoylacetato)-nickel(II) with imidazole, morpholine and their derivatives were synthesised and characterised. The complexes have the general formulae $Ni(BA)_2L_2$ ($L=1\text{-Me}, 1\text{-Et}, 1\text{-Vi}, 1\text{-Pr}, 2\text{-Me}, 2\text{-Et}, 2\text{-IPr}, 1,2\text{-Dime}, 1\text{-Vi}, 2\text{-Me}$ and 4-Me imidazoles and morpholine) and $Ni(BA)_2L.H_2O$ ($L=4\text{-Me}$ and 4-Et morpholine) and have a six-coordinated, trans-pseudooctahedral configuration. The frequencies of $C=O$, $C=C$ and $Ni-O$ absorptions of the $Ni(BA)_2.2H_2O$ undergo a shift in all these mixed ligand complexes. The $C-O-C$ stretching vibration of the free morpholine observed at 1095 cm^{-1} undergoes a positive shift to 1105 cm^{-1} in the complexes showing them to be nitrogen coordinated. The thermogravimetric measurements also reveal the coordination of the neutral base and the benzoylacetate ion. All the complexes are stable at room temperature, but decompose with increasing temperature losing the base and the β -diketonate in definite steps finally forming NiO in an exothermic step around 400° .

THE Nitrogen donor ligands, e.g., imidazole and morpholine, etc., are significant as ligands towards the transition metals because of their biological activity¹. They usually coordinate to the metals as neutral molecules. The bis(β -diketonato) nickel(II) complexes are known to function as Lewis acids and form 5- or 6-coordinated adducts with neutral bases². This paper reports the synthesis and characteristics of a number of six-coordinated imidazole or morpholine base adducts with the formulae $Ni(BA)_2L_2$ or $Ni(BA)_2L.H_2O$, which have a typical green colour, are paramagnetic and possess a pseudo-octahedral structure with the two bases at *trans*, axial positions.

Experimental

The imidazoles and morpholines were supplied by BASF (West Germany). The bis(benzoylacetato) nickel(II) dihydrate was prepared by published method³. Nickel and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods⁴. Carbon and hydrogen were determined by the CDRI, Lucknow. The IR, electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility determinations were carried out as described earlier^{5,6}. The thermoanalytical measurements (tg, dtg and dta) were carried out using a MOM derivatograph (supplied by Hungarian Optical Works, Budapest) in the ambient temperature of the furnace with a heating rate of 10° min^{-1} . The instrument records

simultaneously the temperature (t), thermogravimetry (tg), derivative thermogravimetry (dtg) and differential thermal analysis (dta) curves photographically.

The mixed ligand complexes $Ni(BA)_2L_2$ or $Ni(BA)_2L.H_2O$ were obtained as green compounds by mixing warm methanolic solutions of $Ni(BA)_2.2H_2O$ (1 mole) and the appropriate base (2.5 moles). The mixture was stirred for 10 min, refluxed for 60 min and then the solvent slowly concentrated to yield the desired product, which was collected over a frit, washed with small aliquots of methanol followed by solvent ether and finally dried in *vacuo*.

Results and Discussion

The mixed ligand complexes reported in this paper are shown in Table I. Except for $Ni(BA)_2(4\text{-MeMorph}).H_2O$ and $Ni(BA)_2(4\text{-EtMorph}).H_2O$ in all other cases complexes of the type $Ni(BA)_2L_2$ were formed. This behaviour may be explained on the basis of steric interaction preventing the approach of the two bulky ligands along the axial positions. These complexes are non-electrolytic in Me_2CO , $MeNO_2$ or $PhNO_2$ medium and are of the high spin type. The observed magnetic moments are independent of the field strengths and are thus free from any ferromagnetic impurities⁷. Regular octahedral nickel(II) complexes are known to have

TABLE 1—COLOUR, m.p., AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF BIS(BENZOYLACETONATO) NICKEL(II) WITH IMIDAZOLE AND MORPHOLINE

Compound	Colour	m.p. (°C)	%metal		%nitrogen		μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)	
Ni(BA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	Parrot-green	185	13.9	(14.1)			2.9
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-MeIm) ₂	Light-green	224D	11.2	(10.8)	10.0	(10.3)	2.9
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-EtIm) ₂	Light-green	233	10.1	(10.2)	9.9	(9.8)	3.0
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-ViIm) ₂	Light-green	121	10.4	(10.3)	9.6	(9.8)	3.0
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-PrIm) ₂	Light-green	195	9.8	(9.8)	9.3	(9.3)	3.0
Ni(BA) ₂ (2-MeIm) ₂	Leaf-green	195	10.6	(10.8)	10.1	(10.3)	2.9
Ni(BA) ₂ (2-EtIm) ₂	Deep-green	198	10.0	(10.2)	9.3	(9.8)	3.2
Ni(BA) ₂ (2-IPrIm) ₂	Light-green	220D	9.6	(9.8)	9.0	(9.3)	3.2
Ni(BA) ₂ (4-MeIm) ₂ ^a	Light-green	218	9.9	(10.8)	10.2	(10.3)	2.9
Ni(BA) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ ^b	Deep-green	178	9.8	(10.2)	9.6	(9.8)	2.9
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-Vi2-MeIm) ₂	Light-green	120	9.8	(9.8)	9.2	(9.4)	2.9
Ni(BA) ₂ (Morph) ₂	Light-green	185	10.8	(10.6)	5.0	(5.0)	3.0
Ni(BA) ₂ (4-MeMorph).H ₂ O ^c	Light-green	176	12.0	(11.8)	2.9	(2.8)	3.1
Ni(BA) ₂ (4-EtMorph).H ₂ O ^d	Light-green	160	11.4	(11.4)	2.8	(2.7)	2.9

a. C, 61.7(61.7); H, 5.7(5.5). b. C, 62.6(62.8); H, 5.9(5.9).
 c. C, 59.2(60.0); H, 5.9(6.2). d. C, 60.2(60.7); H, 6.3(6.4).

BA = Benzoylacetate ion, Im = Imidazole, Me = Methyl, Et = Ethyl, Pr = Propyl, IPr = Iso-Propyl, Vi = Vinyl, Morph = Morpholine, D = decomposes without melting.

* Measurement at room-temperature (~300°K)

TABLE 2—THERMO-GRAVIMETRIC MEASUREMENTS OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES

Starting material	Initial decompn. temp. (°C)	T.G.A.		Species formed	DTA peak
		Temp. range (°C)	% Loss Found (Calcd.)		
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-Vi2MeIm) ₂	50	50-155	15.53 (18.21)	Ni(BA) ₂ .L	Endo.
		155-240	38.83 (36.40)	Ni(BA) ₂	Exo.
		240-315	51.76 (49.90)	Ni(BA) _{1.5}	Exo.
		315-380	69.88 (70.10)	Ni(BA) _{0.75}	Exo.
		380-430	88.00 (90.50)	NiO	Exo.
Ni(BA) ₂ (1-PrIm) ₂	60	60-200	10.38 (9.16)	Ni(BA) ₂ .L _{1.5}	Endo.
		200-270	38.93 (36.64)	Ni(BA) ₂	Exo.
		270-440	90.82 (90.20)	NiO	Exo.
Ni(BA) ₂ (2-IPrIm) ₂	40	40-115	7.69 (9.16)	Ni(BA) ₂ .L _{1.5}	Endo.
		115-270	41.01 (36.64)	Ni(BA) ₂	Exo.
		270-400	76.90 (76.83)	Ni(BA) _{0.5}	Exo.
		400-450	90.22 (90.22)	NiO	Exo.
Ni(BA) ₂ (Morph) ₂	50	50-180	14.93 (15.69)	Ni(BA) ₂ .L	Endo.
		180-230	25.09 (23.60)	Ni(BA) ₂ .L _{0.5}	Exo.
		230-315	44.79 (45.98)	Ni(BA) _{1.5}	Exo.
		315-407	83.67 (82.50)	Ni(BA) _{0.5}	Exo.
		407-450	92.58 (89.80)	NiO	Exo.

a ³A_{2g} ground state and since no singlet state from a d-configuration is able to cross it, they always show paramagnetic behaviour. The expected magnetic moments are some 10% above the spin only value and the magnetic moments lie usually in the range 2.9-3.2 B.M.⁶. The experimental magnetic moments of the complexes reported are in the 2.9-3.1 B.M range in agreement with the values predicted and the complexes are thus six-coordinated with an octahedral stereochemistry.

The ligand field spectra of the mixed ligand complexes showed a band of moderate intensity in the 15,000-16,000 cm⁻¹ region, assignable to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F)(ν_2) transition for octahedral nickel(II)

complexes⁶. The other two transitions from the ³A_{2g} level to ³T_{2g}(ν_1) and ³T_{1g}(P)(ν_3) were not observed. An intense UV band around 33,000 cm⁻¹ which is characteristic of the bis-adducts of metal β -diketonates, was observed^{10,11}. The IR spectra of Ni(BA)₂.2H₂O and its mixed ligand complexes with the nitrogen donor ligands recorded in the 4,000-200 cm⁻¹ region exhibited no bands due to the free carbonyl group or free nitrogenous base, indicating them to be coordinated forming a six-coordinate complex. The bands assignable to ν (C=O) and ν (C=C) were observed at 1600 and 1510 cm⁻¹ respectively for the Ni(BA)₂.2H₂O, whereas in the mixed ligand complexes they were shifted to 1590-1595 cm⁻¹ and 1505-1515 cm⁻¹

region, respectively. The Ni–O stretching frequency was observed as two well-localised bands at 590-600 and 415-425 cm^{-1} region, and Ni–N stretching frequency in the 260-280 cm^{-1} region^{1,2}. The IR spectra thus provides evidence for the coordination of the neutral bases to the bis(benzoylacetonato) nickel(II) and the formation of six-coordinated octahedral complexes of nickel(II).

The thermogravimetric measurements of some of these mixed-ligand complexes (Table 2) were studied by the tg, dtg and dta techniques and provided further evidence regarding the coordination of the ligands. All the complexes were fairly stable up to temperatures well above the room temperature and the complexes start losing weight from 60-90° with the loss of the heterocyclic bases and then the β -diketonate ion, ultimately forming the nickel oxide at around 400°.

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